

Development and Validation of Scale to Assess Effective Integration of Information and Communication Technologies during Research Supervision Process at Public sector Universities of Pakistan

Nosheen Kanwal, Shehzad Ahmed, M. Tahir Khan Farooqi

Article Info

Article History

Received:
February 25, 2023

Accepted:
May 26, 2023

Keywords :

ICT, Perceptions, Basic Skills, Practices, Challenges, Supervisors, Supervisees

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.7974801

Abstract

Practice of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has brought incredible advancement in every walk of life especially in progressing countries, which caused enormous change in the role of teachers and learners as well as advancement in the teaching and learning process. The purpose of the study was the development of scale to examine the integration of Information and Communication Technologies during research and supervision process at postgraduate level in public sector universities of Pakistan. The research instrument was developed keeping in view all intricacies and prevailing scenarios. The research instrument encompasses four main factors named as perceptions, basic skills, practices and challenges. The instrument was validated through peer review and subject experts in the field. Finally, 40 items were selected. For pilot testing, 73 supervisees and 35 supervisors were selected from 03 public sector universities through fishbowl method. The scale reliability index was found alpha .892 and .897 whereas component wise range of reliability was .795 to .846 of supervisees' questionnaire and .760 to .828 of supervisors' questionnaire respectively. The strong, positive and significant correlation of each factor showed with overall sum of ICT integration scale during research supervision process.

Introduction

The practice of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has brought incredible advancement in every walk of life especially in progressing countries, which caused enormous change in the role of teachers and learners as well as advancement in the teaching and learning process. Latest ICT applications are playing their role as main component to shape the worldwide economy and carrying out great progressions for mankind (Daniels, 2002). Its range is incomparable in human progress as access to worldwide knowledge, information, communication, enjoyment and facts etc. The advance devices of ICT brought great variety in the communication ways of individuals, consequently various filed such as engineering, education, medicine and business have been changed (Yusuf, 2005). The gadgets of ICT have transformed the education field such as teaching methods, duties of teachers and learners (Mooij, 2007). Developed countries are taking advantages of ICT applications by integrating it in every field but in developing countries like Pakistan, integration of ICT application is low due to limited resources.

Postgraduate students usually conduct research and write project reports or theses so that they can complete their studies. While writing their reports or theses, the students experience different steps and alterations in order to attain the ultimate written piece. Therefore, postgraduate students need certainly to improve their utilization of ICT so that monitoring of their writing progress to completion. Aside from supporting postgraduate research activities, technology also makes post graduate students independent and in a position to progress within their writing with very minimal support from their research supervisors. Additionally, ICT enables quick progression and completion of postgraduate studies because it helps students to gain access to a wide selection of up-to-date information sources in a simple and timely manner, process information quickly and develop good quality reports (Hilkevics & Hilkevics, 2017). To the end, students can get information that permits them to easily hypothesize and test research ideas on their own, make sure validate the theories found in their research, and work independently of the research supervisor, though still with a few supervision.

This shows that using technology, the student has the capacity to do a lot of research work independently, without reverting for their research supervisor after each and every little step; and also this makes their progression easier and faster (Ankamah et al., 2018). Digital learning resources may also be less costly and much more ideal for comfortable access. It is especially helpful to postgraduate students who will be financially constrained to get the mandatory resources; or don't have a lot of time and energy to access the resources from physical libraries inside their institutions (Wallace & Clariana, 2005). Enough time spent going to the library to

find literature for scientific studies are therefore drastically reduced using ICT, and also this translates to faster progression and completion of postgraduate studies.

Uses of ICT in research and supervision process are technically and professionally significant (Manathunga & Lant, 2006). Integration of ICT applications in research process has brought a greater advancement, now the research supervision process is quite different if compared to decades ago (Sim, 2016). Using various latest ICT applications during the process of research and supervision saves time and promote productivity (Bala, 2016). The main challenge in using the ICT applications is the lack of awareness and lack of proper training. The situation is more serious for senior researchers; they usually use manual or traditional methods in the process of research (Castles, 2004). According to Linton (2009), this issue of senior researchers can be solved through providing in-service training sessions and social support. It was further emphasized that once they integrate the technology in research process, they will appreciate and accept the ICT as sign of proficiency.

Moreover, the practices of information and communication technology (ICT) made research work more reliable and usable. Before the practices of ICT and internet, very few students accomplished their degrees of M. Phil and PhD in public sector universities of Pakistan. They had more difficulty to find the literature related to their topics. Supervisors and supervisees used to sit in libraries for many hours to find some related material from the books. Data collection, analysis and interpretation process were manually done which usually took months and sometimes years in the completion of research reports.

In public sector universities of Pakistan, ICT tools (computer and smart devices) have increased the practices of research supervisors and scholars. Murray (2011) stated that ICT refers to the latest information technology in connection to the integration of software, telecommunication, computers and other data system support, transmit and store unified technologies for users to manipulate and access information. It is understood that research students practice ICT throughout their studies, but it is important to know that how they use ICT to help in their research supervision process. Thus, the current study was conducted to develop and validate the scale to investigate the integration process of ICT during research supervision process at public sector universities of Pakistan.

Review of Related Literature

Perceptions or Attitude towards ICT Adoption in Research and Supervision

Perception, in this context, could be the method by which something is considered, understood, or interpreted (Oxford University Press, 2017). To put it differently, it's the impression or attitude grounded about what is believed or observed. Users adopt ICTs use within research for the reason that of the perceived benefits and importance for their research output (Wallace & Clariana, 2005).

Therefore, users' attitude toward the usage of ICT in scientific studies is very imperative to its adoption. The perceived benefits may well not simply be personal into the user but additionally to analyze cohorts or research institutions (Kang et al., 2015). The advantages consist of enhancing the ranking of this institutions, to enhancing the investigation communication and collaboration among researchers across and within institutions, preparing data management policy for a study project and providing researchers support within the storing and sharing data, metadata records and data files (Adeagbo et al., 2016; Arcila-Calderón, Piñuel- Raigada, & Calderín-Cruz, 2013; Bradbury & Borchert, 2010; Dutton & Meyer, 2009; Hellmers, 2009; Meyer & Dutton, 2009).

For instance, Arcila-Calderón et al. (2013) noted that respondents demonstrated a rather great attitude towards e-research, with 69.14% classifying the utilization of digital technologies in research as 'extremely beneficial'. In this way, 47.78% of respondents agreed aided by the statement 'e-research increases my individual productivity' and 53.48% also agreed that 'e-research escalates the productivity of my research group'. Again, Hellmers (2009) found out that significantly more than 70% for the respondents stated that e-research is very important or extremely important for future progress within their research fields.

Similarly, Dutton & Meyer (2009) stated that an optimistic attitude to the role of e-research for the reason that respondents have a tendency to genuinely believe that e-research will not undermine the caliber of research. Additionally, they stated that respondents have a tendency to think that e-research enhances both their personal and their team's productivity (Wallace & Clariana, 2005). The best standard of agreement (59%) has been the declare that 'Many new scientific questions will need the usage e-research tools' suggesting a widespread belief those types of thinking about e-research developments (Wu & Chen, 2012). However, large proportions associated with the respondents indicated they are uncertain about these impacts, saying they 'don't know' or have 'no opinion'.

Adopting advanced ICT in academic institution may be impacted by the perceptions and attitudes of students, researchers and faculty towards it. The use of ICT in studies have caused significant transformation inside our modern world not just given that it really helps to save time and cash used after and during research, but in

addition it reduces the problem in working together with big data or information resources that have been impossible in past times. It has advanced the analysis of research findings (University of Cape Town, 2016).

Basic Skills related to ICT

Based on Pearson and Young (2002), computer literacy is all about the ability to comprehend the broader technological world also to use technological knowledge or power to connect to technology. However, being competent computer users might be more extensive than much research to date assumes (e.g., Gallardo-Echenique, et al., 2015), and even though can find findings in a few studies which regard today's students to be area of the "digital generation" or "digital migrants" (Dobbins, 2005; Kennedy et al., 2009; Prensky, 2001).

There was a standard belief that students entering graduate study, especially PhD study, have appropriate computing skills for study purposes and as a consequence there's no necessity to allow them to take part in computer training programs (Dange, 2010), except perhaps where specialized discipline or task-related software or hardware can be involved. Therefore, M.Phil and PhD scholars' capability to integrate ICT to their research practice is taken for granted, as a result of perceived or assumed readiness caused by their undergraduate and/or Master's study experiences. However, there are some studies showing that lots of graduates cannot cope using the demands of higher education, particularly in terms of ICT use (e.g., Nair & Pillay, 2004; Henderson et al., 2015). In addition, there are also results of their studies suggesting that university students are not efficient at using operational software such as for example learning management systems or office-type applications including Microsoft Excel, PowerPoint, and Access (e.g., Dange, 2010). Another report stated that students had high degrees of ownership of application types however these applications are not frequently employed (Shaw, 2000).

Further, the taken-for-granted perspectives of M.Phil and PhD scholars' capacity to integrate ICT in their research practices align with research indicating that poor preparation when it comes to demands of higher education includes students' meager computer and information literacy skills, "techno-phobia", and low computer literacy or competency (Castles, 2004). Shaw's (2000) report also highlights that graduate students "are taking advantage of the pedagogical features of information technology and get ready for the professional realm of work", and "appropriately anticipating that skills within the use and handling of IT is likely to be needed for advancement along their chosen career paths" (2000, p. 34).

These skills have now been recognized as including: some basic ICT skills, such as for example file management, word processing, spreadsheet manipulation, and graphical presentation (Blignaut & Els, 2010); knowledge of basic components, terms, and conditions, such as for instance basic choice and make use of hardware and software; overcoming techno-phobia; utilization of computer peripherals; basic formatting and editing functions; data entry; error management; usage of operating systems; backing up; and basic network interaction (Blignaut & Els, 2010; Meerah, 2010; Wallace & Clariana, 2005). The questions are then: are M.Phil and PhD scholars conscious of these required ICT skills and therefore are they willing to make use of these skills in the act of undertaking their doctoral research?

Practices of ICT Applications at 6 Core Stages of Research Supervision Process

It is the era of scientific innovations and technology. Every aspect of life got transformed due to the advancement of ICT applications. This all become possible due to the research and development (Rahman, 2011). Due to the Integration of latest ICT applications in the process of research and development brought great advancement and productivity in every respect (Digambarao, 2012).

A tiring, boring and difficult process of research also been transformed due to the advent of latest software and applications specifically designed for the process of research such as online data collection tools, software for quantitative data analysis, software for the analysis of qualitative data, software for the management of references and various databases to access the world class researches (Rahman, 2011). A brief snapshot of various applications being used in the process of research is given below on each phase of research process.

Below given diagram better represents integration of ICT at various stages of research.

Figure 1. Integration of ICT Applications into the Research Supervision Process

ICT Applications and Selection of Research Problem

First step in the process of conducting research is the selection of problem. And every problem has its own background, which can be refined and prepared after the studying the relevant knowledge about that particular topic. Thus, a researcher can better refine or define the research topic problem by accessing the relevant researches in the intended area. For this purpose ICT applications serve in a better way (Bulman & Fairlie, 2016). Various databases, digital libraries, online journals and research repositories can be accessed by using latest ICT applications (Digambarrao, 2012).

ICT Applications and Review of Related Literature

Second phase in the process of conducting research is reviewing the former research work or studies in the particular area from which research topic is selected. Thus, for the purpose of reviewing the relevant research work various ICT applications are used such as digital libraries, online databases, journals and research repositories (Digambarrao, 2012). Hence, advent of various ICT applications brought great advancement and convenience. Now researchers do not need to travel far off libraries to access relevant material. Now world class knowledge can be accessed by single click (Nakhaei et al., 2016).

ICT Applications and Development of Research Instrument and Determining Sample Size

The third step in the process of conducting research is designing the research. At this stage research instruments are developed and population and sample size are determined (Rahman, 2011). Now various website and applications are present which are used for the development of research tools such as questionnaires, interview protocols, psychological tests, checklists, and rating scales (Bulman & Fairlie, 2016). Similarly, various ICT applications are present which determines the sample size automatically.

ICT Applications and Data Collection

The next phase in the process of research is the collection of relevant data. Previously, paper pencil were used to collect data, tools were circulated among the population and were collected physically. These practices take much time, money and effort (Digambarrao, 2012). Now these methods become outdated. Now latest applications and software are present specifically designed; for the purpose of collecting data virtually such as Survey Monkey, Google Form, WhatsApp, Email and many others (Nakhaei et al., 2016).

ICT Applications and Data Analysis

Fifth stage in the process of research is the analysis of data. Data could be in the form of text, contents, documents, videos, audios, opinions, ratings and figures. Broad categories of data are quantitative data and qualitative data (Bulman & Fairlie, 2016). Data analysis applications are present for both types of data. Such as SPSS, SAS, R, Smart PLS and AMOS for the analysis of quantitative data. Similarly, NVivo, MAXQDA, QUIRKOS and MATLAB can analyze qualitative data. Now a researcher can analyze big data sets by single click (Digambarrao, 2012). Thus, latest ICT Applications brought greater convenience in the process of analyzing data.

ICT Applications and Preparing Research Report and Publications

Last stage in the process of doing research is the writing the findings and preparing research report. This task is most critical, crucial and requires academic writing skills (Bulman & Fairlie, 2016). Now presence of latest ICT applications smoothen this process. Various ICT applications are designed specifically for this purpose with guiding tutorial for the users. MS Word offers its services for the formatting of research report according to the requirements of the journals which a researcher approach for publication (Nakhaei et al., 2016).

Challenges in the Integration of ICT during Research Supervision Process in Pakistan

In Pakistan most of the university researchers have to face many challenges during research conduction (Zare-Ee & Shekarey, 2010). Usually, the most common challenges are researcher's interest in technology, supervisor suggestion, insufficient time, confidence in using electronic devices, understanding and abilities in using technology, ineffective training, technical assistance, and the high price of hardware. If software are not present

in the classroom it can cause a serious issue, what teachers and students can do with ICT (AL-Rashed, 2002). According to Mumtaz (2000) limited technological resources within the university are a big problem for conducting research. He added that in 2002 all the universities of Pakistan launched laptops for teachers as initiative. Result of initiative indicated that teachers became integrated for guiding students ICT use.

Lack of Training regarding ICT

In universities there is lack of appropriate training to take full benefits of (ICT), the main factors of training can also be realize in literature as one of the important issue. Al-Rashed (2002) stated that getting benefits from ICT training is not an easy task, benefits of the training must be ensured to the students, teachers and other people belonging to different professions. For teachers and students training is much important. According to Cox, (1999) university teacher needs training in professional development and use technology for teaching purposes, they only know how to turn a computer on and off. According to Oyaid, (2010) University teachers need training to improve students learning. University teachers showed their interest that they must be trained in new technological devices used in the universities like, scanners, printers and digital camera. According to Unal and Ozturk (2012) inadequate training that lack suitable pedagogy is ineffective, commonly; high levels of ICT applications are not used by teachers.

Lack of Infrastructure

Lack of the development of new material for students is a big challenge for students. Lack of instrumentation tools are important issue facing researchers. Lack of infrastructure is very critical issue to those who want to work with new materials (Rahman, 2011). In Pakistan universities need digital libraries and need development more and more digital libraries (Nor & Pearson, 2008).

Unavailability of Guiding Material

In Pakistan there is lack of teleconferencing material in schools, colleges and even at university level. The students and researchers have no opportunities to analyze study problems and create new ideas to develop their learning concepts. Students have lack of guiding material to solve problems because they are not acquiring with ICT tools and its knowledge (Hafeez et al., 2018). They have no guiding material to study together and share their learning experiences with others. ICT learning material is not provided to the students in printed form so ICT teaching-learning do not depend on printed materials. There are multiple materials on Internet. According to Rahman, (2011) ICT materials is not available to transform teaching environment into a student so some time students don't take interest in the learning activities in the ICT classroom.

Technical Challenges

For researcher technical challenges are unexpected equipment problems such as hardware failures or software bugs that create difficulty to conduct research work. Technical challenges can be resolved using available technical skills and expertise. These challenges are easy to identify and define and their solution is very clear (Bala, 2016). Technical challenges connecting the way a machine or system works. During research supervision process. The researchers can have some technical challenges with the new hardware. For researcher some technical challenges are very common such as, device challenge, desktop, computer, laptop, mobile phone, browser challenges, challenges in browsing history and adobe flash player (Ward & Parr, 2010).

Financial Issues

It is identified that financial issues like, lack of suitable funding and support with a lack of satisfactory research services are a big challenge for researchers study production. In Pakistan universities need to encourage their researchers' efforts and provide financial aids to motivate their scholars to conduct better researches (Liew, Foo, & Chennupati, 2000). The major needs for students in universities include suitable incentive, satisfactory research services, financial help for research, and motivation. Many researchers clearly expressed more and more requirements for increasing their own research production. In this way, these researchers think that by increasing research production they would be helped surely because it would increase their scope of study and make them good researchers. Suitable financial support can increase research production and in this way they will be able to develop their status within academic context (Dange, 2010; George et al., 2006).

Lack of Guidance and Motivation

The researchers for conducting research study need guidance and motivation to them working. Lack of guidance and motivation cannot improve researcher's skills of investigation, finding the solutions of study problems and managing accurate result of the study (Heemskerk & Volman, 2012). Most of the times the motivation is enough to keep researcher working on study (Kirkwood, 2014). If no guidance and motivation is present for research, then the quality of research will be very depressing. The researcher has lack of guidance and motivation in the form of lack of logical appeals, lack of emotional appeals, lack of advice and praise. Lack of motivational appeal on provable facts, feeling, right and wrong supervisor remarks (Volman, 2005). Lack of guidance and motivation regarding to ICTs can make the researchers inactive. ICT researcher study and motivation have no direct impact on researchers. Lack of guidance cannot enable the students to communicate with other students (Crook, 2010).

Theoretical Framework

Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) underpins the theoretical framework of the current study. TAM (Technology Acceptance Model) is introduced by Davis in (1989). This is the most widely used models to expose user acceptance performance. Basically this model is applied in social psychology Theory in commonly and the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) in specific. This theory TRA (Theory of Reasoned Action) claims that human beliefs effect attitudes, which lead to objectives and in result create performance/ behavior (Adams et al., 1992).

TAM exposed that the technology acceptance model perceived comfort of use and perceived effectiveness forecast the acceptance of information technology (Davis, 1989). TAM model verified with several applications in tens of studies and has become the most widely applied model of user taking usage. Information technology (IT) adoption has got much attention in the last ten years. Many theoretical models were selected to interpret end-users' acceptance performance but TAM (technology acceptance model) was selected by (Davis, 1989). Now a day's TAM is extensively used and tested. TAM (technology acceptance model) is considered to be more tightfisted, foretelling and forceful (Davis, 1989).

However, literature on TAM and the experiential tests have so far made mixed and inadequate outcomes. These outcomes can be different in term of statistical amount and direction. Technology acceptance model have conducted tens on empirical studies. Whereas, these tens are not special in social sciences. In social sciences human performance is so complex to interpret. The practitioners investigate the antecedents to user acceptance performance. Technology acceptance model can be applicable to all types of technologies.

- **Perceived Usefulness (PU)**, thought as the extent to which a person believes that using a method will enhance his job performance (Venkatesh & Bala, 2008).
- **Perceived simplicity of use (PEOU)**, thought as the extent to which a person believes that using a method is going to be without any effort (Venkatesh & Bala, 2008).

Figure 2. Technology Acceptance Model

Purpose of the study

The purpose of the study was to develop and validate two scales to investigate about perceptions, basic skills, practices and challenges of supervisors and supervisees regarding ICT integration during conducting research supervision process and writing their final dissertation at postgraduate level such as M. Phil and Ph. D.

Methodology

This section describes the different phases of scale development such as sampling procedure, item development, validation and results.

Sampling Procedure

Seventy three supervisees and thirty-five supervisors were selected using simple random sampling method (fishbowl method) from the population. Due to prevailing situation of COVID-19 questionnaires were administered through WhatsApp. Reminders were given to the participants for filling up the questionnaires.

Development of the Research Instruments

For the purpose of developing research instruments, a detailed literature was reviewed and focus-group discussions were conducted with the population such as research scholars and faculty members who were supervising post-graduate research scholars during their research work. After focus-group discussions and literature review four themes were emerged; perceptions, basic skill, practices and challenges. Again literature was searched on these four factors and items were developed on each factor. Some of factors were directly adopted whereas some of the items were adapted according to the context. Initially, at least 80 to 90 items were developed on each factor that was reduced to 10 after certain modifications, customization, discussions with peers and expert opinions of the subject matter experts.

Validation of the Research Instruments

To validate the research instrument researcher conducted peer review with PhD scholars. After a thorough consultation and discussion with scholars many of items were removed from the both questionnaires due to similarity and repetition reasons. After that researcher accessed three English language experts for opinion regarding language and grammatical corrections. After getting feedback from English language expert, certain modifications were incorporated in both questionnaires. Then, Subject Matter Experts (SME) were accessed regarding expert opinion about the content. In this regard, 2 head of department of Computer Sciences and 1 head of department of Education were consulted. After getting feedback from subject matter experts some statements were removed and some statements were rephrased in questionnaires; questionnaire for supervisors and questionnaire for supervisees.

After validation of research instrument, it was named as Information and Communication Technology Integration in Research Supervision Process Scale ICTI-IRSPS for supervisors and supervisees. To check the reliability of scale, pilot testing process was conducted by the researcher. Each statement has five-point Likert response, i.e., strongly disagree (SD), disagree (D), neutral (N), agree (A), and strongly agree (SA).

Pilot Testing of the Research Instruments

To check the reliability of both questionnaires, questionnaire for supervisors and questionnaire for supervisees, researcher pilot tested the both questionnaires. Both questionnaires were administered on five-point Likert scale. Each item had 5 options such as strongly disagree, disagree, neutral, agree and strongly agree.

Procedure of the Pilot Testing

For the purpose of pilot testing, seventy three supervisees and thirty-five supervisors were selected using simple random sampling method (fishbowl method) from the population. Due to prevailing situation of COVID-19 questionnaires were administered through WhatsApp. Reminders were given to the participants for filling up the questionnaires.

Results

Factor Analysis

For the purpose of measuring construct validity, rotated component factor analysis was conducted on both questionnaires, questionnaire for supervisors and questionnaire for supervisees. Below given table shows the statements loaded with their components.

Table 1. Rotated Component Matrix, Statements Loaded with their Component of ICTI-IRSPS for Supervisors

No.	Factor Loading	Perceptions	Basic Skills	Practices	Challenges
1	Using ICT provide convenience in communication	0.56			
2	Using ICT promote collaboration	0.41			
3	Using ICT saves time	0.75			
4	Organizing information is easy by using ICT	0.65			
5	Using ICT promote productivity	0.85			
6	Using ICT is essential to live and work in 21 st century	0.79			
7	Using ICT promote autonomy in researcher	0.54			
8	Using ICT promote smart work	0.63			
9	ICT plays vital role in research supervision process	0.78			
10	Using ICT improve my research supervision skills	0.57			
11	I can write a paragraph using word processing program		0.43		
12	I can use email to communicate with others		0.76		
13	I can capture digital photos, movies and other graphics		0.59		
14	I can edit text online containing internet links and images		0.79		
15	I can create database		0.60		
16	I can organize computer file in folder and sub-folders		0.47		
17	I can create a spreadsheet with simple graphs		0.68		
18	I can create a presentation with simple animation functions		0.51		
19	I can participate in a discussion forum on the internet		0.75		
20	I can download and install a software		0.42		
21	I communicate with scholars using different ICT apps such as Email, Skype, WhatsApp, etc.			0.78	
22	I use Track Changes option in MS Word to give feedback to scholars on their research work			0.47	
23	I evaluate supervisees' work and give feedback online			0.52	
24	I created online discussion forum for my supervisees to interact other researchers			0.41	
25	I guide scholars about different search engines such as Google Scholar, Wikipedia, Yahoo, Ask.com, etc.			0.59	
26	I guide scholars about different digital libraries; Internet Archive, Open Library, World Digital Library			0.75	
27	I use Google Classroom to upload different assignment, schedules and deadlines for supervisees			0.47	
28	I teach scholars about the formatting of document			0.62	
29	I guide scholars about different quantitative and qualitative data analysis software			0.51	

30	I use Turnitin to detect plagiarism in students' work	0.75
31	I don't have adequate training of using ICT	0.58
32	I don't have pedagogical support for using ICT	0.66
33	I face technical issues such as lack of internet connection, poor infrastructure pirated software, etc.	0.73
34	I don't have adequate guiding material for using ICT	0.61
35	I face issues in understanding the available guiding material as material is not in national language	0.58
36	I don't have confidence to use ICT	0.76
37	I don't have any motivation for using ICT	0.61
38	Frequent use of ICT cause health problems	0.47
39	I don't have financial resources for using ICT	0.77
40	Too much time consuming to search relevant material by using ICT	0.59

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis. Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization. Rotation converged in 5 iterations.

The table 1 shows that statements 1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10 were loaded at the component 1 (perceptions regarding integration of ICT applications in the research supervision process), statements 11,12,13,14,15,16,17,18,19,20 were loaded at the component 2 (basic skills regarding various ICT applications being used in the research supervision process), statements 21,22,23,24,25,26,27,28,29,30 were loaded at the component 3 (practices of various ICT applications during research supervision process) and the statements 31,32,33,34,35,36,37,38,39,40 were loaded at the component 4 (challenges regarding integration of ICT applications in the research supervision process).

Table 2. Rotated Component Matrix, Statements Loaded with their Component of ICTI-IRSPS for Supervisees

No.	Items	Factor Loading			
		Perceptions	Basic Skills	Practices	Challenges
1	Using ICT provide convenience in communication	0.78			
2	Using ICT promote collaboration	0.61			
3	Using ICT saves time	0.85			
4	Organizing information is easy by using ICT	0.65			
5	Using ICT promote productivity	0.55			
6	Using ICT is essential to live and work in 21 st century	0.69			
7	Using ICT promote autonomy	0.74			
8	Using ICT promote smart work	0.82			
9	ICT plays vital role in research process	0.68			
10	Using ICT improve my research skills	0.37			
11	I can write a paragraph using word processing program		0.58		
12	I can use email to communicate with others		0.46		
13	I can capture digital photos, movies and other graphics		0.65		
14	I can edit text online containing internet links and images		0.75		
15	I can create database		0.69		
16	I can organize computer file in folder and sub-folders		0.57		
17	I can create a spreadsheet with simple graphs		0.69		
18	I can create a presentation with simple animation functions		0.51		
19	I can participate in a discussion forum on the internet		0.85		

20	I can download and install a software	0.72	
21	I use different search engines such as Google Scholar, Wikipedia, Yahoo, Ask.com, etc.		0.68
22	I use digital libraries; Internet Archive, Open Library, World Digital Library, etc.		0.41
23	I use Pakistan Research Repository to access different Thesis, Textbooks and Research Journals		0.62
24	I access different online journals such as JSTOR, ScienceDirect, Taylor & Francis, etc.		0.46
25	I use online data collection tools such as Survey Monkey, Type form, Survey Planet, Survey Gizmo, SoGoSurvey, etc.		0.59
26	I use different software for analysis of quantitative data such as, SPSS, STATA, SAS, MATLAB, etc.		0.35
27	I use different software for the analysis of qualitative data such as, NVivo, MAXQDA, Quirkos, Qualtrics, etc.		0.77
28	I use different software for reference management such as Mendeley, EndNote, Zotero, RefWorks, JabRef, etc.		0.44
29	I use different plagiarism checker software such as Grammarly, Article Checker, Turnitin, DupliChecker, etc.		0.31
30	I use different ICT applications for submission of my research report for publication such as Elsevier, Wiley, Sage Publications, etc.		0.55
31	I don't have adequate training of using ICT		0.48
32	I don't have pedagogical support for using ICT from supervisor		0.66
33	I face technical issues such as lack of internet connection, poor infrastructure pirated software, etc.		0.63
34	I don't have adequate guiding material for using ICT		0.51
35	I face issues in understanding the available guiding material as material is not in national language		0.48
36	I don't have confidence to use ICT		0.56
37	I don't have any motivation from supervisors in using ICT		0.61
38	Frequent use of ICT cause health problems		0.47
39	I don't have financial resources for using ICT		0.57
40	Too much time consuming to search relevant material by using ICT		0.79

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis. Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization. Rotation converged in 5 iterations.

The table 2 shows that statements 1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10 were loaded at the component 1 (perceptions regarding integration of ICT applications in the research supervision process), statements 11,12,13,14,15,16,17,18,19,20 were loaded at the component 2 (basic skills regarding various ICT applications being used in the research supervision process), statements 21,22,23,24,25,26,27,28,29,30 were loaded at the component 3 (practices of various ICT applications during research supervision process) and the statements 31,32,33,34,35,36,37,38,39,40 were loaded at the component 4 (challenges regarding integration of ICT applications in the research supervision process).

Items Breakup of ICTI-IRSPS for Supervisors

Research instrument for supervisors were developed to measure the practices and challenges of supervisors regarding the incorporation of latest applications of ICT in the process of research and supervision at public sector universities of Pakistan. There were 40 items with 4 factors related to practices and challenges (research instrument is given in the Appendix). They were; perceptions with 10 items, basic skills with 10 items, practices with 10 items and also 10 items for challenges. The items division is given in table 3.

Table 3. Items Breakup of ICTI-IRSPS for supervisors

Sr. No.	Factors	Item Numbers
1	Perceptions	1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10
2	Basic Skills	11,12,13,14,15,16,17,18,19,20
3	Practices	21,22,23,24,25,26,27,28,29,30
4	Challenges	31,32,33,34,35,36,37,38,39,40

Items Breakup of ICTI-IRSPS for Supervisees

Research instrument for supervisees were developed to measure the practices and challenges of supervisees regarding the incorporation of latest applications of ICT in the process of research and supervision at public sector universities of Pakistan. There were 40 items with 4 factors related to practices and challenges (research instrument is given in the Appendix). They were; perceptions with 10 items, basic skills with 10 items, practices with 10 items and also 10 items for challenges. The items fragmentation is given in table 4.

Table 4. Items Breakup of ICTI-IRSPS for Supervisees

Sr. No.	Factors	Item Numbers
1	Perceptions	1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10
2	Basic Skills	11,12,13,14,15,16,17,18,19,20
3	Practices	21,22,23,24,25,26,27,28,29,30
4	Challenges	31,32,33,34,35,36,37,38,39,40

Reliability of ICTI-IRSPS for Supervisors

Below give table 5 illustrate the total as well as component wise internal consistency about questionnaire for supervisors.

Table 5. Reliability of ICTI-IRSPS for supervisors (Component wise and Complete)

Scale for Supervisors	Reliability
Perceptions	.797
Basic Skills	.828
Practices	.804
Challenges	.760
Overall	.897

Above table illustrate that the total reliability of research tool for supervisors is .897. This value is good enough for using the research tool to collect data. The component wise range of reliability was .797 to .828.

Reliability of ICTI-IRSPS for Supervisees

Below give table 6 illustrate the total as well as component wise internal consistency about questionnaire for supervisees.

Table 6. Reliability of ICTI-IRSPS for Supervisees (Component wise and Complete)

Scale for Supervisees	Reliability
Perceptions	.838
Basic Skills	.795
Practices	.810

Challenges	.846
Overall	.892

Above table illustrate that the total reliability of research tool for supervisors is .892. This value is good enough for using the research tool to collect data. The component wise range of reliability was .795 to .846.

Table 7. Correlation among Factors of ICTI-IRSPS for Supervisors

Correlation among factors				
	Perception	Basic Skills	Practices	Challenges
Perception	1.00			
Basic Skills	0.69	1.00		
Practices	0.83	0.75	1.00	
Challenges	0.68	0.84	0.77	1.00

Table 8. Correlation among Factors of ICTI-IRSPS for Supervisees

Correlation among factors				
	Perception	Basic Skills	Practices	Challenges
Perception	1.00			
Basic Skills	0.58	1.00		
Practices	0.63	0.79	1.00	
Challenges	0.74	0.83	0.72	1.00

Discussion and Conclusion

The use of ICT in scientific studies are anticipated to equip postgraduate researchers when they look at the university with world-class expertise and facilities within the collection and handling of research data; modeling, simulation and data processing through high-performance computing; comprehension of big data through visualization and data science techniques; dissemination of research outcomes that features data and workflows; promotion of collaborative research through virtual labs and cloud resources plus the growth of customized research software, hardware and services (Jackson, 2005). Clearly, this innovation would be to provide applications and services to assist postgraduate students, faculty and university community inside their research endeavors. Consequently, the rates from which ICTs are used by African Universities may have positive effect on the amount of support to electronic materials and application by academic researchers. Easily put, we are able to argue that the adoption of ICT in postgraduate research will contribute immensely into the realization of institutional goals through the provision of adequate and effective information towards the university community.

Uses of ICT in research and supervision process are technically and professionally significant (Manathunga & Lant, 2006). Integration of ICT applications in research process has brought a greater advancement, now the research process is quite different if compared to decades ago (Sim, 2016). Using various latest ICT applications during the process of research and supervision saves time and promote productivity (Bala, 2016). The main challenge in using the ICT applications is the lack of awareness and lack of proper training. The situation is more serious for senior researchers; they usually use manual or traditional methods in the process of research (Castles, 2004). According to Linton (2009), this issue of senior researchers can be solved through providing in-service training sessions and social support. It was further emphasized that once they integrate the technology in research process, they will appreciate and accept the ICT as sign of proficiency.

Therefore, need is to develop scale to identify or investigate how researchers and supervisors perceive the integration of ICT in research and supervision process, what level of basic skills they have regarding ICT, to what extent they practice ICT integration and what type of specific challenges they confront while integrating ICT during research supervision process. Available scales regarding ICT are in the context of teaching, learning and classroom management which do not address the intricacies of research and supervision process. Thus, keeping in view the existing scenario scales for supervisors and supervisees regarding ICT integration during research supervisions process were developed after reviewing existing scales and literature and all intricacies are added in the scale which are compulsory part of research and supervision process in public universities of Pakistan.

As this scale was used in 03 public sector universities. It is recommended that this may be used in further public private universities to assess the effective integration of ICT during the research supervision process and to know about the challenges supervisors and supervisees confront while using ICT.

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Author Information

Nosheen Kanwal

PhD Scholar, Department of Educational Research and Assessment (DERA), Faculty of Education, University of Okara, Okara

Dr. Shehzad Ahmed

Assistant Professor, Department of Educational Research and Assessment (DERA), Faculty of Education, University of Okara, Okara

Dr. M. Tahir Khan Farooqi

Associate Professor, Department of Educational Research and Assessment (DERA), Faculty of Education, University of Okara, Okara
